

***Polysphincta idukkiensis* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Pimplinae) a rare new species from the southern Western Ghats**

***Manjusha B.M.¹, Sudheer K.² & Ghosh S.M.³**

¹ *Research Scholar, Department of Zoology, Government College Kasaragod, Vidyannagar, Kerala, India.*

² *Assistant Professor in Zoology, Prof. T.C. Narendran Biodiversity Research Lab., The Zamorin's Guruvayurappan College, Kozhikode, Kerala, India.*

³ *Department of Molecular Biology, Kannur University, Kerala, India.*

(Email: manjushabm@gmail.com)

Abstract

The members of the genus *Polysphincta* are koinobiont parasitoids exclusively associated with free living spiders. The genus is currently represented by three valid species from the Oriental region, viz., *Polysphincta boops* Tschek, 1869, *P. longa* Kasparyan, 1976 and *P. punctigaster* Varga & Reshchikov, 2015. In the present paper *Polysphincta idukkiensis* sp.n. is described from the Pambadum shola forests of Idukki district, a part of the southern Western Ghats of India. The species is closely related to *P. boops* Tschek in having impunctate swelling on metasomal tergites, but it differs from *P. boops* Tschek in having shallow close punctures on propodeum, and also on the length of ovipositor sheath. A key to the Oriental species of *Polysphincta* Gravenhorst, 1829 is provided.

Keywords: *Polysphincta*, Key, India, new species, new record, Ichneumonidae.

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Introduction

The genus *Polysphincta* was erected by Gravenhorst in 1829 with the type species *Polysphincta tuberosa*. *Polysphincta* is a relatively small genus of the tribe Ephialtini under the subfamily Pimplinae of family Ichneumonidae and is represented by 28 described species (Yu *et al.*, 2012; Varga & Reshchikov, 2015). They are koinobiont parasitoids exclusively associated with free living spiders. The genus is currently represented by three valid species from the Oriental region, viz., *Polysphincta boops* Tschek, *P. longa* Kasparyan and *P. punctigaster* Varga & Reshchikov. Varga and Reshchikov (2015) synonymized *P. asiatica* Kusigemati, 1984 to *P. boops* Tschek. All the known species are strictly associated with species of the family Araneidae (Fitton *et al.*, 1988; Yu *et al.*, 2012).

Many of them have multiple host species, with the exception of *P. longa*, which has only one host species (Fitton *et al.*, 1988; Schmitt *et al.*, 2012; Yu *et al.*, 2012; Fritzen and Shaw 2014; Korenko *et al.*, 2014). In the present paper, a new species of *Polysphincta*

viz., *P. idukkiensis* sp.n., is described from the Pambadum shola forests of Idukki district, a part of the southern Western Ghats.

Materials and Methods

The current study is based on material collected from the Pambadum shola forests. Morphological terminology used in the study follows that of Townes (1969) and of Wahl and Sharkley (1993). Images were taken using Leica Stereomicroscope model no: M205 A.

Abbreviations used:

FWL- Fore Wing Length
FWW- Fore Wing Width
HWL- Hind Wing Length
HWW- Hind Wing Width
T- Tergites (T1-T8)

WGRC: Western Ghats Regional Centre of the Zoological Survey of India, Kozhikode, Kerala

The type specimen is currently deposited in the Prof. T.C. Narendran Biodiversity Research Laboratory (NBRL), University of Calicut, Kozhikode and will be transferred to the WGRC, ZSI, Kozhikode.

Figures 1-6. *Polysphincta idukkiensis* sp.n.: 1. Lateral view of habitus; 2. Front view of head; 3. Dorsal view of mesoscutum and propodeum; 4. Wings; 5. Dorsal view of metasoma; 6. Lateral view of ovipositor

Taxonomy

Genus *Polysphincta* Gravenhorst, 1829

Diagnosis: Upper tooth of mandibles longer than lower tooth. Clypeus transverse, apically centrally truncate. Head more or less evenly rounded. Mesoscutum convex, from densely pubescent to smooth and glabrous. Mesopleuron with prepectal carina present. Propodeum moderately long, usually without carinae. Fore wing with areolet open, second intercubitus absent, nervulus opposite to basal vein. Hind wing with discoidella present. Metasoma with tergite 1 slightly elongate, all four tergites shining with punctures between antero lateral swellings. Ovipositor straight or

slightly sinuous, projecting beyond the apex of metasoma.

Polysphincta idukkiensis Manjusha,
Sudheer & Ghosh sp.n. (Fig.1-6)

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:74DF0C26-AE52-4771-866F-436BA6D634DD](https://zoobank.org/act:74DF0C26-AE52-4771-866F-436BA6D634DD)

Description: Female: body length= 7.2 mm (Including ovipositor)

Head: In dorsal view HL= 1.45 mm and HW = 0.56 mm; in front view HL= 1.7 mm and HW= 1.5 mm; face with sparse punctures,

hairy, interstices smooth and shiny; clypeus apically truncate, with long hairs; mandible with upper tooth longer than lower, hairs smaller than in face, 0.45x high as wide; malar space polished, 0.7x the basal width of mandible; vertex convex, polished, impunctate, with small few hairs; occipital carina complete; temple and gena impunctate with small hairs; diameter of lateral ocellus 0.75x long as ocellar ocular distance; inter-ocellar distance 0.67x ocellar ocular distance, 0.76x distance between median and lateral ocelli; antenna with 27 segments, scape 1.44x as long as width, 1.5x as long as pedicel, pedicel 0.21x as long as first flagellar segment, first flagellar segment 1.45x as long as second flagellar segment, 5x as long as last flagellar segment, second flagellar segment equal to the length of third flagellar segment.

Mesosoma: 1.7x long as head length in dorsal view, 0.9x as long as width between tegulae; pronotum polished, epomia present, almost reaching upper margin of pronotum; mesoscutum impunctate, few hairs on anterio-lateral and posterior side; notauli distinct on anterior 0.2 of mesoscutum; scutellum convex, impunctate, with sparse hairs; mesopleurum polished, impunctate, few hairs on upper anterior and middle, speculum smooth and shiny, lower region with more hairs than anterior upper; prepectal carina present on lower 0.5 of mesopleurum; metapleurum impunctate, polished with sparse hairs; submetapleural carina complete and strong; propodeum with shallow close punctures, posteriorly with declivities without carina, hairs present; propodeal spiracle elongate; legs slender; FWL= 3.28 mm, FWW= 1.72 mm, HWL= 2.08 mm, HWW= 1.51 mm; areolet open; second intercubitus absent, nervulus opposite to basal vein, intercepted below 0.12; nervellus complete; discoidella present.

Metasoma: T1 1.4x as long as apical width, 1.2x length of T2, T1 with deep coarse punctures, hairs on lateral side, ventro-lateral carina present, apical area smooth and shiny; T2–T7 a pair of swelling without punctures, smooth and shiny, with apical area smooth and shiny, remaining area with coarsely punctures; T8 with small minute punctures, smooth and shiny with hairs; legs slender, hind leg with femur 4x long as wide, 0.74x long as hind tibia, first tarsomere 2.8x long as second, 5.1x long as third tarsomere, 7.75x long as fourth tarsomere, 3.87x long as fifth tarsomere and

third tarsomere 0.75x long as fifth tarsomere; ovipositor straight, upper valve basally broadened, lower valve extending beyond upper valve, tip of lower valve with oblique ridges; ovipositor length 2.2 mm; ovipositor sheath 1.45x hind tibia, densely pubescent.

Colour: Head and face black except antennal base and lateral side of scape yellow, and brownish black clypeus; mesoscutum reddish brown, scutellum yellowish white, brownish-yellow anteriorly, post-scutellum whitish-yellow, pronotum black, mesopleurum and metapleurum reddish brown; propodeum reddish brown; first tergite black, T2–T6 reddish brown, apices of T2, T3 black, T7 and T8 black; all coxae whitish yellow; hind tibia with sub basal and apical brown bands; tarsi brownish yellow at their apices, ovipositor reddish brown with sheath black.

Male: Unknown; **Host:** Unknown

Material examined: Holotype: ♀, INDIA: KERALA, Idukki, Pambadamshola (N 10°07'34"- E 77°14'58"), Sweep net, 8.iv.2016, Coll. Bijoy, Reg No: NBRL/PIM/19232.

Etymology: The species is named after the type locality, Idukki a district of Kerala.

A key to the Oriental species of the genus

Polysphincta Gravenhorst

1. Ovipositor sheath 1.45x long as hind tibia; propodeum with shallow close punctures.....***P. idukkiensis* sp.n.**
 - Ovipositor sheath < 1.4x long as hind tibia; propodeum usually impunctate, if punctures present sparse.....**2**
2. Tergites 3-6 with two anterolateral swellings densely punctate, anteriorly and between swellings sparsely punctate.....
 -***P. punctigaster* Varga & Reschikov**
 - Tergites 3-6 with two anterolateral swellings impunctate, anteriorly and between swellings indistinctly granulate with small punctures.....**3**
3. Central lobe of mesoscutum shorter and rounded, mesoscutum highly pubescent; propodeum impunctate.....
 -***P. longa* Kasparayan**
 - Central lobe of mesoscutum elongate and flat, mesoscutum sparsely pubescent; propodeum sparsely punctate.....
 -***P. boops* Tschek**

Discussion

Polysphincta idukkiensis sp.n. shows following variations with *P. boops*. In *P. idukkiensis* sp.n., ovipositor sheath 1.45x long as hind tibia whereas in *P. boops*, it is 1.1-1.4x long as hind tibia. Propodeum of *P. idukkiensis* sp.n. has close shallow punctures and virtually bare in posterior declivities but in *P. boops* propodeum weakly and very sparsely punctate on anterior half, virtually bare on posterior half. In *P. idukkiensis* sp.n., nervellus is intercepted at lower 0.12 and in *P. boops* nervellus is intercepted at lower 0.37-0.5. Hind femur stouter, 4x long as wide in lateral view in *P. idukkiensis* sp.n. (In *P. boops*, hind femur slender, 5.3- 5.9 x long as wide).

The new species is also similar to *P. longa* Kasparyan in having mesoscutum without dense hairs on posterior region of median lobe, but differs in having propodeum with close shallow punctures and impunctate swellings on T1-T7. *Polysphincta idukkiensis* sp.n. differs from *P. punctigaster* in having impunctate swelling on T2-T7, (In *P. punctigaster* punctate swelling on T3-T6).

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